

Heat transfer unusual dependence on boundary scattering in very long narrow conductors

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When modeling heat transfer in nanoribbons, an unusually sharp dependence of the heat flux, and, consequently, the thermal conductivity coefficient, on the degree of specularity of phonon reflection from the lateral boundaries was found. From numerical calculations, it followed that the addition of minimally diffuse scattering should lead to an abrupt increase in the thermal resistance of the conductor. Given the importance of selecting optimal thermal parameters in nanotechnology, this short paper provides an analysis of the found dependencies, discusses the physical reasons for this anomalous behavior, and draws conclusions about the importance of achieving the quality of the nanoconductor interface to create thermal contacts with a given or optimal thermal conductivity.

Keywords: nanoribbons, specular reflection, diffusive reflection, phonons, heat flow.

1. Introduction

The dependence of the efficiency of heat transfer in two-dimensional nanoribbons on the length and width of the sample was studied in detail in [1, 2] for the case of purely diffuse reflection from the boundary. It should be noted that the diffuse reflection limit, in which the phonon is reflected from the boundary isotropically in all directions, provides maximum thermal resistance. This occurs because in this case, the maximum number of phonons (exactly half) experiences back reflection concerning the direction of the incident phonon. The reverse limit is the case of specular reflection [3, 4]. In this case, reverse reflection is in principle impossible, since, by the definition of specular reflection, the phonon momentum component directed along the reflecting boundary does not change.

The actual reflection of a phonon from a non-ideally smooth wall can be described as some kind of superposition of these two limiting cases. In the simplest model [4] the concept of the probability of specularity of reflection p is introduced, which is equal to unity for the specular case and zero for the opposite diffuse limit.

2. Model of the system

To describe the phonon system under consideration, we introduce the concept of distribution functions of incident phonons f_{inc} and reflected phonons f_{spec} . The connection between them in the case of mirror reflection is given by the following relations:

$$f_{\text{spec}}(k_z, k_x) = f_{\text{inc}}(k_z, -k_x). \quad (1)$$

Here, the vector $\mathbf{k} = (k_x, k_z)$ is the wave vector of the phonon. In this case, the z axis is chosen along the sample boundary and the x axis is perpendicular to the boundary.

In the case of pure diffuse reflection, it is assumed that the distribution of reflected phonons is completely isotropic, i.e., all angles of reflection are equally likely:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{\text{diff}}(k_z, k_x) &= f_{\text{diff}}(k \cos \phi, k \sin \phi) = f_{\text{diff}}(k, \phi) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \eta(0 \leq \phi \leq \pi) \int_0^\pi f_{\text{inc}}(k, \tilde{\phi}) \sin \tilde{\phi} d\tilde{\phi}. \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, k is the length of the wave vector, and the angle ϕ is measured from the positive direction of z axes (it is the angle

between the boundary and direction of phonon motion). The function $\eta(0 \leq \phi \leq \pi)$ (so-called unitary rectangle function) describes the uniform distribution of reflected phonons over the entire range of angles from zero to π . In the variables, k and ϕ , relation (1) takes the form

$$f_{\text{spec}}(k, \phi) = f_{\text{inc}}(k, \phi). \quad (3)$$

According to the model used in [4], in the intermediate case, the distribution function of reflected phonons has the form

$$f_{\text{refl}}(k, \phi) = pf_{\text{spec}}(k, \phi) + (1-p)f_{\text{diff}}(k, \phi). \quad (4)$$

As a system under study, we consider long nanoribbons, whose length exceeds the width by 10–100 times. When a stationary heater is turned on, which ensures a constant temperature on one side, and a cooling thermostat on the other side (see Fig. 1), a stationary heat flow will occur in the heat conductor. The magnitude of this flow is determined both by the dimensions of the nanoribbon and the properties of its edges, or more precisely, by the properties of the interaction of heat carriers — phonons — with the edges.

To determine this heat flux, it is necessary to determine the dependence on the longitudinal coordinate (in our case, the z coordinate) of the distribution function of phonons incident on the boundary $F_{\text{inc}}(z, \phi)$. In the approximation of the ballistic regime, when phonons interact only with the edges and do not interact with each other, we can limit ourselves to phonons of the same wavelength. For this reason, we omit the dependence of the distribution function on the phonon momentum. The distribution function $F_{\text{inc}}(z, \phi)$ is formed due to phonons that arrive at a given point on the wall directly from the heater, and phonons that arrive at this point after reflection from the opposite boundary. These two groups of phonons correspond to two terms in the following formula:

$$F_{\text{inc}}(z, \phi) = g_h(z, \phi) + F_{\text{ref}}(z - W \text{ctg} \phi, \phi) \eta(0 < z - W \text{ctg} \phi < L). \quad (5)$$

Here, L and W are the length and width of the rectangular nanoribbon (see Fig. 1). The $g(z, \phi)$ describes the flow of phonons that arrive at a given point on the boundary directly from the heater.

The second term includes the distribution function $F_{\text{ref}}(z, \phi)$ of phonons reflected from the edge at a point with the corresponding z coordinate. In turn, this function

Fig. 1. (Color online) The geometry of the problem.

is completely determined by relation (4), which for coordinate-dependent distribution functions can be rewritten as

$$F_{\text{ref}}(z, \phi) = pF_{\text{inc}}(z, \phi) + \frac{1}{2}(1-p)\eta(0 \leq \phi \leq \pi) \times \int_0^\pi F_{\text{inc}}(z, \tilde{\phi}) \sin \tilde{\phi} d\tilde{\phi}. \quad (6)$$

The resulting relations (5) and (6) formally represent a system of equations for determining the unknown functions $F_{\text{inc}}(z, \phi)$ and $F_{\text{ref}}(z, \phi)$. The solution of this system and the subsequent determination of heat flows and thermal conductivity coefficient are carried out using numerical methods or approximate analytical methods [2].

3. Discussion of the results

The numerical solutions of the above equations show that for conductors with small ratios between the width W and length L , the dependences of heat fluxes on the value p of the surface specularity turn out to be quite smooth functions. The dependence of both the heat flow and the thermal conductivity coefficient on the parameters of the problem reflected well-known physical tendencies. For example, increasing the length or decreasing the width leads to a decrease in heat transfer, at least because such a change in geometric dimensions increases the likelihood of a phonon returning to the heater. In turn, an increase in the reflection diffuseness coefficient leads to an increase in the reverse movement of phonons due to reflection, which also leads to a decrease in the heat flow through the conductor.

However, for the case of sufficiently long conductors $L/W > 10$, an unusually sharp dependence of the heat flux, and, consequently, the thermal conductivity coefficient, on the degree of specularity of phonon reflection from the lateral boundaries was discovered. The results of numerical calculations are given in Table 1 for the temperature difference at the edges of the sample dT , heat flux Q_c , and heat transfer coefficient $K = Q_c/dT$ for different values of p and the different W/L ratios.

From numerical calculations, it followed that the addition of minimally diffuse scattering should lead to an abrupt increase in the thermal resistance of the conductor.

An example of this behavior of the heat transfer coefficient at p near to 1 is shown in Fig. 2(a). To discuss the physical reasons for this behavior, consider the heat flow in this limit, which is shown in Fig. 2(b).

As a possible explanation, we can consider a mechanism that is realized in one-dimensional conductors in the presence of scattering centers [5]. In this case, we identify the probability of backward scattering with the parameter $(1-p)$ and the length of the conductor with the number of scattering centers N . In this case, the product $N(1-p)$, which stands in the relation (12) from Ref. 5 can be replaced by the value $aL(1-p)/W$ for our problem. Then for the magnitude of

Table 1. The results of numerical calculations for different parameters of nanoribbon

p	$W/L = 0.01$			$W/L = 0.03$			$W/L = 0.05$			$W/L = 0.08$		
	dT	Q_c	K									
1	0	1	infinite									
0.999	0.13	0.96	7.4	0.057	0.98	17.2	0.04	0.987	25	0.028	0.99	36
0.995	0.32	0.84	2.6	0.175	0.93	5.3	0.126	0.96	7.57	0.092	0.97	10.6
0.993	0.38	0.8	2.13	0.214	0.91	4.26	0.157	0.94	6.0	0.115	0.96	8.35
0.99	0.44	0.75	1.7	0.262	0.88	3.37	0.196	0.92	4.7	0.146	0.95	6.5
0.9	0.81	0.32	0.4	0.657	0.52	0.8	0.567	0.62	1.1	0.48	0.71	1.47
0.7	0.912	0.15	0.16	0.819	0.3	0.37	0.752	0.39	0.52	0.423	0.48	0.71
0.5	0.95	0.1	0.1	0.875	0.2	0.24	0.822	0.29	0.35	0.759	0.365	0.48

the heat flux for the case of long conductors with low diffuse scattering, it will be possible to propose such an approximate formula:

$$Q_c = \frac{p}{p + a \frac{1-p}{W/L}} = \frac{p}{p + N_{\text{eff}}(1-p)}, \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2. (Color online) Dependences of the heat transfer coefficient (a) and heat flow (b) on the boundary specularly parameter for different W/L ratios.

where the fitting coefficient turned out to be equal to $a = 0.4$.

The calculation using this formula is shown in Fig. 2(b) from which one can see good qualitative agreement between the dependence and the results of numerical calculations. From this we can conclude that long conductors with extremely low diffuse backscattering can be considered as practically one-dimensional conductors containing a large number of scattering centers

$$N_{\text{eff}} = a \frac{L}{W} \quad (7)$$

with a very low backscattering coefficient $(1-p)$.

4. Conclusion

Finally, modeling heat transfer in nanoribbons, an unusually sharp dependence of the heat flux, and, consequently, the thermal conductivity coefficient, on the degree of specularly of phonon reflection from the lateral boundaries was found. From numerical calculations, it followed that the addition of minimally diffuse scattering should lead to an abrupt increase in the thermal resistance of the conductor. To describe this effect, a model was proposed in which such thin conductors were considered as a set of successive scattering centers, the number of which is proportional to the length of the conductor, and the forward scattering coefficient at such a scattering center is equal to the specularly coefficient of the boundary.

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Незвичайна залежність теплопередачі від граничного розсіювання в дуже довгих вузьких провідниках

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При моделюванні теплообміну в нанострічках виявлено надзвичайно різку залежність теплового потоку, а також коефіцієнта теплопровідності від ступеня дзеркальності відбиття фононів від бічних границь. Численні розрахунки свідчать, що додавання мінімального дифузного розсіювання призводить до різкого збільшення теплового опору провідника. З огляду на важливість вибору оптимальних теплових параметрів у нанотехнологіях, у цій статті наводиться аналіз виявлених залежностей, обговорюються фізичні причини такої аномальної поведінки та робляться висновки про важливість досягнення якості границь напівпровідників для створення теплового контакту із заданою або оптимальною теплопровідністю.

Ключові слова: нанострічки, дзеркальне відбиття, дифузійне відбиття, фонони, тепловий потік.